

Supplementary Material

What Makes Life for Process Mining Analysts Difficult? A Reflection of Challenges

Authors: Lisa Zimmermann, Francesca Zerbatto, Barbara Weber

Last updated by the authors: 23.08.2023

The following material provides additional information to section 3) *Method*.

As part of our research, we conducted two data collections. For both, we followed the empirical standards:

1. Interview Study: <https://github.com/acmsigsoft/EmpiricalStandards/blob/master/docs/QualitativeSurveys.md>
2. Questionnaire Survey: <https://github.com/acmsigsoft/EmpiricalStandards/blob/master/docs/QuestionnaireSurveys.md>

Interview Study

The goal of the paper is to derive process mining challenges and complement existing research on challenges in process mining with an individual perspective. To uncover the challenges of process mining analysts, we therefore conducted an interview study to learn more about the individual hurdles that analysts perceive in their projects.

1 - Interview Protocol

(T): To be asked referring to the process mining task (G): To be asked referring to general work practices

1. ACTIVITIES, TARGET ARTIFACTS and USE of ARTIFACTS

- Can you briefly summarize the main steps of your analysis today and explain why you worked in this way? (T)
- Would you always follow the same steps in practice? (G)
- What information did you aim to gather during the analysis? Why? (T)
- Would you always focus on gathering the same information in practice or does that change from case to case? (G)
- How did you use the provided artifacts during the analysis? Why were they useful? (T)

2. GOALS

- Can you summarize the main goals of your analysis today? (T)
- Do you always work with these goals in mind in practice? (G)
- Do you always have clear analysis goals or objectives in practice? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that the analyses you conduct in practice are exploratory? By exploratory we mean that you spend time refining research questions, generating new questions for the analysis.

3. STRATEGIES, START and TERMINATION CRITERIA

- Did you follow any specific strategy (plan of action to achieve a certain goal) when trying to answer the questions today? (T)
- Did your analysis approach change during the analysis? If so, how? (T)
- Would you follow the same approach in practice, with other event logs? (G)
- How did you decide where to start your analysis from? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually choose where to start your analysis from? (G)
- How did you decide that it was time to stop the analysis? Did you follow any criteria? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually decide that it is time to stop the analysis? (G)

4. CHALLENGES

- Is there anything that you found challenging during the task today? (T)
- And in general, what do you think are the biggest challenges of process mining? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that good tool knowledge helps to overcome process mining challenges? (G)

- Do you think that combining different process mining tools is an opportunity for the analysis or do you think it is too complicated/not needed? (G)
- Taking a look at process mining, where do you think there is more need for methodological or operational support? (G)

2 – Participant’s Selection

Based on the guidelines in (Mason, 2010), we aimed to collect between 30 and 50 participants for the interview study. To identify challenges relevant in practice, we require participants to have hands-on experience with process mining analysis and to be familiar with one of the commonly used process mining tools. As we want to learn from experts and include participants with different backgrounds (e.g., academics and practitioners) working in different areas, we limited ourselves to the following inclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Having analyzed at least two real-life event logs in the two years prior to the study.
2. Being knowledgeable of at least one of the following tools: bupaR, Celonis, Disco, PM4Py, ProM (i.e., the process mining tools available for the process mining task which is not part of this paper – further information can be found in Zerbato (2022)).

Sampling strategy:

We identified participants by listing candidates from our personal networks and the networks of our project partners. We balanced people working in different organizations and with different job profiles. We invited participants via e-mail in which we described the purpose of the study, the requirements for participation, the estimated time-effort, and the procedure of the data collection.

Out of the 48 invitations we initially send, 40 replied and 30 agreed to participate (response rate: 83.3%; acceptance rate: 62.5%), as others either did not meet the inclusion criteria or had time constraints. 5 of the participants shared further contacts with us which helped us to reach out to another 30 potential participants. Out of them, 17 replied to our e-mail and 11 people agreed to participate in the study (response rate: 56.7%; acceptance rate: 36.6%). The main reasons for declining were again that people did not meet the participation requirements or had time constraints.

Saturation:

We stopped collecting data when we achieved data saturation (Saunders, 2018), i.e., we noticed that answers were repeating across interviews and that patterns in reported challenges were emerging.

Examples:

- 1) Question Formulation

P6: “And it should be the way it should be the way you should have a research question to answer. It’s because it directs to in the correct way to analyze and you know, what to focus on. When you don’t have any question, you’re not focused and your analysis would not be correct. Maybe you go this way, that way and you don’t know what to do. But having questions is really important.”

P18: “Like when it is based on a question, because in my experience, not only in process mining but general data analysis, that if you don’t really have a question, it’s very hard to come up with interesting patterns.”

P24: "The first thing that I read was the goal, because it's the most important thing when doing anything out of this task. Because otherwise you can spend hours, hours and hours doing something that doesn't have an impact, and even if you find a nice insight, you need to have the impact."

2) Data Quality:

P6: "Data has many issues. Most of the time they got issues, quality issues. So, just understanding the quality issues and fixing them is a big challenge for me."

P18: "I think the most important challenge is data quality of event data, which is often not very good."

P38: "Ok, one is the data quality. I mean, it's always like a challenge."

3 - Participant Overview

The table contains the overview of the 41 participants (**p**) of the study. It highlights the **sector**, to which the participant's affiliation/company belongs, the participant's job **role** at the time of the data collection, **years of experience** in process mining and data science, the **self-rated expertise** of the participant in **process mining** and **process analytics** (ranked on a Likert-scale with values "novice", "basic", "average", "good", "advanced"), the **number of process mining tools the participant knew**, and the **number of analyzed event logs** two years prior to the data collection.

Participant	Sector	Role	Experience		Expertise		# known Tools	# analyzed event logs (in past 2 years)
			in Process Mining (in years)	in Data Science (in years)	Process Mining	Process Analytics		
p1	Enterprise Software	Product Manager	2	Up to 1	Good	Basic	1	1
p2	Academia	PhD Student	1	1-3	Average	Average	3	1
p3	National Laboratory	Senior R&D Staff	3	> 10	Good	Average	2	2-5
p4	Consulting	Senior R&D Staff	2	6-10	Average	Average	3	1
p5	Consumer Goods	Process Analyst	2.5	Up to 1	Average	Average	1	2-5
p6	Freelance	Process Mining Consultant	2	1-3	Good	Good	2	2-5
p7	Academia	Professor	10	6-10	Advanced	Average	3	6-10
p8	Academia	Assistant Professor	10	4-5	Advanced	Good	2	2-5
p9	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	3.5	1-3	Good	Good	2	> 20
p10	Academia	Senior Researcher	1	None	Novice	Novice	1	None
p11	Freelance	Business Analyst	8	> 10	Advanced	Advanced	4	6-10
p12	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Good	4	2-5
p13	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	1	Up to 1	Basic	Basic	1	1
p14	Enterprise Software	Product Manager / Engineer	3	1-3	Good	Good	1	10-20
p15	Academia	Assistant Professor	6	6-10	Good	Average	3	2-5
p16	Academia	PhD Student	4	None	Average	Average	2	2-5
p17	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	4	1-3	Good	Average	1	10-20
p18	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	4	6-10
p19	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	4	6-10
p20	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	0.3	Up to 1	Basic	Basic	1	1
p21	Academia	Graduate Student	3	1-3	Average	Average	4	None
p22	Academia	Graduate Student	0.3	1-3	Basic	Basic	1	1
p23	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	1	Up to 1	Average	Average	2	2-5
p24	Enterprise Software	Analytics Product Manager	3	1-3	Good	Good	1	2-5
p25	Food Processing	Process Analyst	4	> 10	Good	Good	2	2-5
p26	Packaging	Digital Project Manager	7	1-3	Good	Good	1	2-5

p27	Financial	Process Mining Analyst	1	1-3	Average	Average	5	2-5
p28	Academia	Professor	4	> 10	Good	Good	4	2-5
p29	Academia	PhD Student	6	6-10	Good	Average	5	2-5
p30	Academia	Professor	10	1-3	Average	Good	5	2-5
p31	Telecommunications	Business Consultant	2	> 10	Basic	Good	1	2-5
p32	Academia	PhD Student	2	1-3	Average	Basic	2	2-5
p33	Constructions	Operational Excellence Lead	3	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	1	6-10
p34	Government	Consultant	10	> 10	Good	Good	2	6-10
p35	Insurance	Process Analyst	2	Up to 1	Good	Good	1	2-5
p36	Academia	PhD Student	6	1-3	Good	Good	3	2-5
p37	Insurance	Operational Excellence Lead	5	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	1	> 20
p38	Academia	Professor	8	4-5	Good	Good	4	6-10
p39	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	5	10-20
p40	Academia	Senior Researcher	16	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	4	> 20
p41	Academia	PhD Student	7	6-10	Good	Advanced	2	2-5

4 - Coding Examples

To analyze the interviews, we followed a grounded theory approach and coded the interviews in three rounds.

1) In-Vivo Coding

In the first round, used "In-Vivo" coding and highlighted statements about challenges.

2) Axial Coding

In the second round, we used axial coding to draw connections between the statements so that first categories emerged.

3) Selective Coding

In the final coding round, we further merged categories and removed categories supported by statements of less than 4 interviewees to reduce our list to relevant challenges.

The full coding scheme can be found in CodingScheme_InterviewStudy.xlsx

Questionnaire Survey

The goal of the paper is to derive process mining challenges and complement existing research on challenges in process mining with an individual perspective. To validate challenges derived from the interview study and add further context for them, we conducted a questionnaire survey to identify whether the challenges are understood and experienced in practice. Additionally, we aim to understand their relevancy and how they are tackled in practice.

1 – Respondent’s Selection

We aimed to collect between 20 and 30 responses for the questionnaire survey. To validate challenges and gain information about their relevancy and how they are mitigated, we require respondents to be experienced in the conduct of process mining projects. As we want to learn from experts and include participants with different backgrounds (e.g., academics and practitioners) working in different areas, we limited ourselves to the following inclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Having at least one year of experience in process mining.
2. Having actively worked on at least one of the project phases described by Emanjome et al. (2019).

Sampling strategy:

We identified respective participants by listing candidates from our personal networks. We balanced people working in different organizations and with different job profiles. We invited participants via e-mail and described the purposes of the study, the requirements for participation, the estimated time-effort, and the procedure of the data collection.

Additionally, we shared the link to the survey vial social media groups such as the process mining group on LinkedIn¹. In the professional network, tool vendors, professionals and academics share relevant articles with the community. The group has more than 14.600 members (as of Dec. 2022) and was identified as highly relevant as a target group for the survey. We posted a link to the study there and within two weeks’ time re-posted the call.

As we shared the link publicly, we cannot provide the response rate. The data collection lasted from 29.07.2022 – 16.10.2022. In this period, 53 interviews were started out of which 38 answered the mandatory demographics questions (71.7%). 3 of the 38 respondents did not indicate sufficient experience and were prompted to the end of the questionnaire. Another 11 respondents did not reply to any of the detailed questions per challenges and were therefore also excluded, resulting in a total of 24 valid responses (dropout rate: 54.7%).

2 - Respondents Overview

The table contains the overview of the **24 respondents** of the questionnaire survey. It highlights the **industry**, to which the participant’s affiliation/company belongs, the participant’s **job role** at the time of the data collection, the **range of conducted process mining projects** and the **years of experience in process mining**, the self-rated **expertise** of the participant **in process mining and in process analytics**

¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/1915049/>

(ranked on a Likert-scale with values "novice", "basic", "average", "good", "advanced"), the **number of project phases the participant actively contributed to** in a project (each selected for "Question Formulation", "Data Collection", "Data Preparation", "Mining & Analysis", "Stakeholder evaluation", "Implementation"), and the **number of challenges the respondent provided feedback for** during the questionnaire survey.

ID	Industry	Role	Experience		Expertise		No. of Phases	No. rated challenges
			No. Projects	Years	Process Mining	Process Analytics		
105	Academia	N/A	6-10	3-5	Advanced	Advanced	4	20
106	Academia	N/A	1-2	1-2	Basic	Basic	3	17
164	Cybersecurity	Research Associate	1-2	3-5	Good	Good	3	10
180	Consultancy	Consultant	3-5	1-2	Good	Good	5	7
181	Health care	Transformation Manager	1-2	3-5	Good	Good	6	8
182	Consultancy	Consultant	6-10	3-5	Advanced	Good	5	6
184	Consultancy	Consultant	3-5	1-2	Average	Average	4	13
185	Academia	Researcher	1-2	1-2	Good	Average	4	9
186	Consultancy	Business Analyst	3-5	6-10	Good	Good	6	6
197	Software Provider	N/A	3-5	3-5	Average	Average	3	3
210	Education	Process Analyst	3-5	1-2	Basic	Good	3	1
214	Information services	Process Mining Specialist	6-10	1-2	Good	Good	6	14
222	Information services	Director	>10	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	6	11
225	Consultancy	Consultant	3-5	1-2	Advanced	Average	5	12
245	Academia	Assistant professor	1-2	1-2	Average	Average	1	2
247	Academia	Researcher	1-2	3-5	Good	Good	4	6
251	Academia	Researcher	3-5	3-5	Good	Good	5	10
252	Academia	N/A	3-5	6-10	Average	Average	2	10
269	Academia	Researcher	3-5	1-2	Average	Good	2	14
270	Food services	Process Analyst	3-5	1-2	Good	Average	5	6
278	Information services	Researcher	3-5	3-5	Advanced	Advanced	5	10
299	Information services	Director	>10	3-5	Good	Good	6	22
313	Consultancy	Consultant	>10	3-5	Advanced	Advanced	6	5
314	Cross-industry	Customer Value Architect	3-5	1-2	Average	Average	1	4

4 – Questionnaire Instrument

A PDF version of the full questionnaire can be found in the QuestionnaireInstrument.pdf

References

Mason, M. (2010). *Sample Size and Saturation in PhD Studies Using Qualitative Interviews*. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-11.3.1428>

Saunders, B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T. et al. Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization. *Qual Quant* 52, 1893–1907 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-017-0574-8>

Emamjome, F., Andrews, R., ter Hofstede, A.H.M. (2019). A Case Study Lens on Process Mining in Practice. In: Panetto, H., Debruyne, C., Hepp, M., Lewis, D., Ardagna, C., Meersman, R. (eds) *On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems: OTM 2019 Conferences. OTM 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science()*, vol 11877. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33246-4_8

Zerbato, F., Soffer, P., Weber, B. (2022). Process Mining Practices: Evidence from Interviews. In: Di Ciccio, C., Dijkman, R., del Río Ortega, A., Rinderle-Ma, S. (eds) *Business Process Management. BPM 2022. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 13420. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-16103-2_19